

Enhancing Product Lifecycle Efficiency: Harnessing Natural Language Processing for Materials Insight and Optimization

Inés Pérez Couñago, Lara Suárez Casabiell, Andrea Gregores-Coto, Christian Eike Precker and Santiago Muiños-Landin*

^aAIMEN Technology Centre, C/Relva, 27 A. Torneiros – 36410 Porrino – Pontevedra, Spain

* Corresponding author. E-mail address: santiago.muinos@aimen.es

Materials play a pivotal role in manufacturing, serving as the foundation upon which the functionality, durability, and overall quality of products are built, highlighting the critical significance of material selection and utilization in the manufacturing process. In the material science domain, an overwhelmingly amount of knowledge is generated and stored as text encoding a humongous amount of information related with materials performance along the product life cycle that results fundamental in the current manufacturing landscape, addressing adaptability and circularity. This study explores the application of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to analyse data availability [2,3,4], with a specific focus on the domain of polyvinyl chloride (PVC) materials across chemical, environmental, health, social and economic dimensions. While acknowledging the expanse of available academic data, this research also ventures into exploring big data sources, including regulatory pages such as those of REACH or EPA, not often emphasized in the existing literature.

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) is employed to autonomously extract interconnected topics from textual data, providing a flexible tool to structure multifaceted datasets [5]. The study highlights LDA's capability in effectively distinguishing between diverse topics within PVC-related documents, facilitating the identification of sources offering information on each dimension of interest. Furthermore, the integration of LDA with question-and-answer schemes, powered by Large Language Models (LLMs), represents a step forward in comprehensive data mapping [1]. This integration aids in expediting the extraction of relevant information while contributing to the creation of a structured database where all relevant information pertaining to a particular topic is organized, identifying specific missing data or non-correlated information.

This work underscores the potential of NLP in navigating complex data landscapes. This approach promises to contribute to the evolution of data analysis methodologies, offering insights into the data landscapes of material science with large impact in the current manufacturing scenario.

Keywords: materials; natural language processing; product lifecycle; sustainability

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